

Synthetic and mechanistic aspects of reactions of complexed chromium(VI) compounds

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Manuscript received 13 July 2000, revised 5 February 2001, accepted 5 June 2001

Oxidation of organic compounds is an important transformation in synthetic organic chemistry. Chromium(VI), in the form of inorganic dichromates, has long been used in organic chemistry as an oxidizing agent. However, due to its drastic nature and requirement of strong acidic solution, attempts have been made to develop mild, selective and efficient Cr^{VI} derivatives. Collin's and Corey's reagents were the first ones to be reported. Their discovery has led to an enhanced interest in field of organic derivatives of chromium(VI) as oxidizing agents. A large number of such derivatives have been reported. Most of them are reasonably stable, soluble in many organic solvents and convenient to use. Mechanistic studies of the reactions of the complexed Cr^{VI} reagents were first reported in 1978. Thereafter, much work in this field has been reported. The field of organic derivatives of Cr^{VI} is still receiving attention from different laboratories across the world. In this review, both the synthetic and mechanistic aspects of the chemistry of complexed Cr^{VI} compounds, have been brought into sharp focus.

A close examination of the area of conversion of alcohols to carbonyl compounds reveals the emergence of the theme centring around the preparation and use of oxidizing agents which function as mild oxidants and afford easy separation of the unreacted and reacted oxidizing agent from the desired products. The dipyridine-chromium(VI) oxide complex¹ and the pyridinium chlorochromate complex (Corey's reagent or PCC)² have been studied extensively for such purposes, and have been employed both in synthetic and kinetic studies.

The first review pertaining to the use of novel chromium(VI) reagents for the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols appeared in 1982, which summarized the salient features of several hexavalent chromium compounds³. Subsequently, a review highlighting the oxidizing properties of PCC as a versatile oxidant in organic synthesis, was published⁴. Both these reviews stressed the importance of chromium(VI) reagents used for the operational-ly simple oxidation of alcohols to carbonyl compounds.

Undoubtedly, the most significant attributes of an oxidizing agent would be its requirement to be mild enough to leave acid-sensitive protecting groups intact and sufficiently selective in sparing easily oxidizable functions. Thus, the search for mild, versatile, selective reagents for the conversion of alcohols to carbonyl compounds has been the primary objective of many research laboratories.

In this review, we aim to discuss the synthetic and mechanistic aspects of the chemistry of complexed

chromium(VI) compounds. Our attempt has been to cover the recent literature. Since the synthetic aspects of PCC have already been reviewed⁴, we have touched that reagent very briefly, only to highlight some recent developments.

Synthetic aspects

2,2'-Bipyridinium chlorochromate :

The usefulness of chromium(VI) reagents in organic synthesis was indicated in the preparation of two new reagents, viz., 2,2'-bipyridinium chlorochromate (BPCC) and 2,2'-bipyridinechromium trioxide complex⁵. These reagents have proved to be instrumental in simplifying the isolation of the resulting carbonyl compounds, and were found to be especially useful in the oxidation of compounds with acid-sensitive protecting groups, due to the internal buffering of the 2,2'-bipyridyl system.

4-(Dimethylamino)pyridinium chlorochromate :

Synthetically useful changes in the properties and reactivity of chromium(VI) reagents could be effected by varying the amine ligand associated with chromium trioxide. This concept resulted in the preparation of a new chromium(VI) reagent which enhanced the selectivity of the earlier two bipyridyl Cr^{VI} complexes. This reagent, 4-(dimethylamino)pyridinium chlorochromate (DMAP. HCrO₃Cl) is selective in its slow oxidation of primary alcohols relative to allylic or benzylic alcohols⁶.

Pyridinium fluorochromate :

Pyridinium fluorochromate (C₅H₅NHCrO₃F or PFC)

was found to have certain advantages over similar oxidizing agents in terms of amounts of oxidant and solvent required, short reaction times, and high yields⁷. PFC in dichloromethane oxidizes primary and secondary alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds in high yields, anthracene to anthraquinone, benzoin to benzil, a tricyclic allylic alcohol to a tricyclenone and triphenylphosphine to the corresponding oxide⁸. It was later shown that like PCC, PFC also is a two-electron oxidant and the end-product is a Cr^{IV} species⁸.

Bis[benzyltriethylammonium]dichromate :

Potassium or sodium dichromates are active in sulfuric acid solutions. However, these are inadequate for the oxidation of acid-sensitive compounds. Tetraalkylammonium salts have been used for oxidation purposes. A highly selective oxidant was prepared which found effective for the oxidation of alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds, and mercaptans to disulfides in neutral organic solutions. This reagent, bis[benzyltriethylammonium]dichromate, is capable of effecting the oxidation of acid-sensitive alcohols⁹.

1,8-Naphthyridinium chlorochromate and pyrazinium chlorochromate :

In 1983, two new chlorochromate complexes, viz. 1,8-naphthyridinium chlorochromate (C₈H₆N₂HCrO₃Cl or NapCC) and pyrazinium chlorochromate (C₄H₄N₂HCrO₃Cl or PzCC) were synthesized and characterized¹⁰. These complexes were formed as solid crystalline precipitates when an aqueous solution of CrO₃, containing a molar equivalent of HCl, was added to an aqueous solution of 1,8-naphthyridine or pyrazine, respectively (containing one molar equivalent of HCl) at 0°. These solid products are quite stable, non-hygroscopic, and could be stored in the dark for three months. These could be readily separated from the desired organic products and are milder oxidants than PCC. A study of the oxidative behavior of NapCC and PzCC, relative to PCC, with primary and secondary alcohols revealed that PzCC is a much milder oxidant than PCC, and that NapCC is milder than PzCC.

Tertrakis(pyridine)silver dichromate :

Keeping in mind that the nature of the cation and the ligands attached to it could affect the oxidation ability of the oxoanion, tetrakis(pyridine)silver dichromate (Py₄Ag₂Cr₂O₇ or TPSD) was synthesized with a view to minimize the difficulties experienced in handling some of the earlier chromium(vi) complexes when used for oxidizing organic compounds¹¹. This reagent is quite stable and non-hygroscopic at room temperature, and is not photosensitive. Being neutral, it was found suitable for the oxidation of acid-sensitive compounds. It is soluble in water, pyridine, acetone and acetonitrile. TPSD oxidizes benzylic and allylic alcohols to their corresponding carbonyl compounds

in 80–100% yields, the reaction time varying between 0.5 and 3 h.

Benzotriazole-mediated chromium(vi) oxidations :

The formation of amine complexes had resulted in synthetically useful changes in the properties and reactivity of chromium(vi) reagents. For example, PCC has been shown to form complexes with pyridine¹², other aromatic amines¹³, pyrazole¹⁴, and 3,5-dimethylpyrazole (DMP)¹⁵ which selectively oxidized steroidal allylic alcohols to the corresponding ketones. The first report of the use of a triazole to mediate selective chromium(vi) oxidations established the synthetic utility of such reactions¹⁶. Benzotriazole used in conjunction with PCC was found to be effective for the rapid and selective oxidation of steroidal allylic alcohols to the corresponding ketones.

Benzotriazole-chromium trioxide complex :

Benzotriazole was found to complex with chromium trioxide to produce a versatile new oxidant. This complex was found capable of oxidizing primary alcohols to carboxylic acids, secondary alcohols to ketones, and olefin substrates to α,β -unsaturated ketones by allylic oxidation¹⁷. Farnesol could be converted to the corresponding acid. Other amine-CrO₃ complexes have been reported to produce aldehydes from primary alcohols.

Nicotinium dichromate and isonicotinium dichromate :

In the efforts to use new chromium(vi) reagents under mild and anhydrous conditions, two new chromium(vi) compounds were prepared, which were derived from nicotinic and isonicotinic acids. Nicotinium dichromate (NDC) and isonicotinium dichromate (INDC) were found to oxidize alcohols to carbonyl compounds, thiols to disulfides, and hydroquinones to quinones¹⁸. The significant observation was that the reaction time decreased when pyridine was added to a suspension of the reagent and the substrate, in dichloromethane as solvent. Under the same conditions, when pyridinium dichromate (PDC) was used instead of NDC, the oxidation rate was unaffected. Thus, NDC and INDC, in the presence of pyridine, are good oxidants for a wide variety of alcohols. In contrast, oxidations with PDC were unaffected or retarded, in the presence of pyridine.

Peroxyacetic acid in the presence of 2,4-dimethylpentane-2,4-diol cyclic chromate as catalyst :

It seemed advantageous to develop oxidizing agents which require only catalytic amounts of Cr^{VI}. A new and highly efficient combination for the conversion of secondary alcohols to ketones was reported. The reagent consists of peroxyacetic acid as the stoichiometric oxidant, in the presence of a catalytic amount of 2,4-dimethylpentane-2,4-diol cyclic chromate, using a solvent mixture containing carbon tetrachloride and dichloromethane¹⁹. It was observed that longer reaction times were required for hindered

secondary alcohols, e.g. oxidation of borneol to camphor, which suggested that for sterically screened hydroxyls, mixed chromate ester formation may be rate-limiting.

Halosilanes chromium trioxide :

A new class of chromium(VI) reagents, derived from chromium trioxide and halosilanes, was prepared²⁰. These reagents are highly efficient for the oxidation of alcohols to carbonyl compounds, for the oxidative coupling of mercaptans to disulfides, and for a mild cleavage of oximes to carbonyl compounds.

When equimolar amounts of trimethylchlorosilane and powdered chromium trioxide were mixed, an orange-red solution was obtained. This is diluted with dichloromethane, and dry nitrogen is bubbled through the solution to remove traces of hydrogen chloride. The reagent thus prepared has been used for the various oxidative transformations. The oxidation of alcohols with dimethylchlorosilane-chromium trioxide (I), diphenyldichlorosilane-chromium trioxide (II) and dimethyldichlorosilane-chromium trioxide (III) gave the corresponding carbonyl compounds. The results are compiled in Table 1. These reagents were also used for the oxidative cleavage of some oximes. The generality of this method was indicated by the fact that benzaldoxime gave a high yield of benzaldehyde without further oxidation.

Table 1. Oxidation of alcohols by halosilanes/CrO₃

Substrate	Reagent	Time min	Yield %
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ OH	I	45	81
	II	60	66
4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ OH	III	60	76
4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ OH	I	40	93
	II	60	57
4-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ OH	I	180	87
(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ CHOH	III	90	92
	II	240	61
C ₆ H ₅ -CH-NOH	I	10	72
	III	120	45
4-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ -CH-NOH	I	15	60
4-ClC ₆ H ₄ -CH=NOH	I	35	79
	III	60	66
(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ C=NOH	I	105	65

Imidazolium dichromate :

The chromium trioxide-imidazole complex was found to behave as an oxidant. Imidazolium dichromate is a mild selective reagent for the oxidation of allylic and benzylic alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds in high yields²¹. This reagent is prepared by adding imidazole to a solution of an equimolar amount of chromium trioxide in a minimum amount of water, and is obtained as yellow crystals. The reagent is soluble in DMF and DMSO.

Pyridinium bromochromate :

Apart from being efficient as an oxidant for alcohols, pyridinium bromochromate (PBC) also functions as a good

brominating agent for aromatic compounds²². PBC has been reported to oxidize primary and secondary alcohols to the aldehyde/ketone in 70–95% yields in 3–4 h.

Tetraalkylammonium chlorochromates :

As phase transfer catalysis (PTC) technique for the oxidation of alcohols under mild acidic conditions has been reported. The addition of CrO₃ in HCl to a solution of the quaternary ammonium salt of benzyltriethylamine in dichloromethane gives the benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate (BTMACC)²³.

In a comparative study of several chromium(VI) reagents, which oxidized alcohols under slightly acidic or neutral conditions, the following reagents were examined : PFC, BTMACC and tetrabutylammonium chlorochromate (TBACC). It was observed that only PFC was as reactive as PCC, and the oxidation took place at 25°. The reaction with BTMACC was sluggish at 25°, and the complete oxidation required heating at 80° in 1,2-dichloroethane. TBACC was marginal in its reaction, while other reagents such as tetramethylammonium chlorochromate, tetramethylammonium fluorochromate and tetrabutylammonium fluorochromate were inert for the oxidation of alcohols²⁴. Some results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Oxidation of alcohols to the carbonyl compounds with PFC, BTMACC or TBACC

Alcohol	Oxidant	Conditions		Yield(%) of carbonyl compd.
		Temp °C	Time h	
4- <i>t</i> -Butylcyclohexanol	PFC	25	6	92
Cyclododecanol	PFC	25	6	93
	BTMACC	80	10	97
	TBACC	80	30	68
PhCH(OH)Me	PFC	25	6	88
4-Dodecanol	PFC	25	8	96
1-Dodecanol	PFC	25	6	78
	BTMACC	80	10	92
	TBACC	80	30	58
	PFC	25	2	96
Carveol	BTMACC	80	4	87
	TBACC	80	2	72
	PFC	25	2	80
Geraniol	BTMACC	80	6	83
	TBACC	80	3	58
	PFC	25	2	82
Borneol	PFC	25	8	77
3 β -Cholestanol	PFC	25	6	96
	BTMACC	80	10	98

Quinolinium dichromate :

Quinolinium dichromate (QDC) was found to be useful for the selective oxidation of primary and secondary al-

cohols to aldehydes and ketones, respectively²⁵. QDC is soluble in water, DME and DMSO.

Chromium peroxide complexes :

Chromium peroxide complexes have been prepared and used for the oxidation of organic compounds. Chromium peroxide etherate (CPE), pyridinechromium peroxide (PCP), and 2,2'-bipyridylchromium peroxide (BPCP) have all been used for the oxidation of alcohols to the carbonyl compounds²⁶. The generality of these oxidants in organic synthesis was shown by the different kinds of substrates which underwent oxidation. Diols underwent C-C bond cleavage, α -hydroxyacids were decarboxylated, oximes were converted to their carbonyl compounds, thiols to disulfides, aromatic amines to azo compounds, anthracene and phenanthrene to their quinones. Some comparative data are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Oxidation of organic compounds with BPCP, PCP and CPE

Substrate	Oxidant	Time h	Yield %
Benzyl alcohol	BPCP	1.0	95
	PCP	0.5	100
	CPE	1.0	85
Benzhydrol	BPCP	1.0	95
	PCP	0.5	65
	CPE	0.7	90
Cyclohexanol	BPCP	3.0	85
	PCP	1.5	95
	CPE	1.0	85
2-Octanol	BPCP	4.0	80
	PCP	1.25	90
1-Heptanol	BPCP	4.0	90
	PCP	1.25	90
	CPE	1.0	80
Cinnamyl alcohol	BPCP	1.25	100
	PCP	2.0	90
	CPE	1.5	30
Benzilic acid	BPCP	0.7	100
	PCP	0.3	100
	CPE	0.5	90
Benzylamine	BPCP	0.4	100
	PCP	2.5	50
Anthracene	BPCP	7.0	60
	PCP	5.0	30

Biphosphonium dichromate :

Biphosphonium dichromate (BPDC) was found to be a mild and selective reagent for the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols. Primary alcohols were oxidized to the aldehyde, and geraniol underwent oxidation without isomerization or migration of the double bond²⁷.

Another reagent of this category, butyltriphenylphosphonium dichromate (BTPPD) was reported by Baltork *et al.*²⁸ in 1997. BTPPD is a mild and selective oxidizing agent. It efficiently oxidizes alcohols to carbonyl compounds, thiols to disulfides, aromatic amines to azo compounds and aromatic oximes to the corresponding carbonyl compounds.

Other chlorochromates :

With a view to providing further evidence to ascertain the mechanism of oxidation of alcohols by Corey's reagent, some new Cr^{VI} reagents were synthesized. These reagents are 1-methylimidazolium chlorochromate (MCC), imidazolium chlorochromate (ICC), and isoquinolinium chlorochromate (IQC). It was found that these reagents are similar in selectivity. The mechanism for the oxidation of alcohols by these reagents is similar to that for the oxidation of alcohols by PCC^{29,30}.

In a related work, Agarwal *et al.*³¹ described an improved preparation of PCC. Their method involved the initial formation of pyridinium hydrochloride by reacting pyridine with conc. HCl, and then treating it with chromic oxide. They claimed that this method avoided the formation of toxic chromyl chloride, and the yield of PCC was better. For the oxidation of alcohols, the reaction time was reduced by half when the reaction was carried out in the presence of catalytic amounts of anhydrous acetic acid.

Recently, Chakraborty and Bordoloi³² found that in the absence of any solvents, PCC could oxidize alcohols to carbonyl compounds, and regenerate carbonyl functions from oximes, under microwave irradiation.

Metal dichromates :

Zinc dichromate trihydrate [ZnCr₂O₇] in dichloromethane was found to be a mild reagent for the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols to the corresponding aldehydes and ketones in good yields. Allylic alcohols and tricyclic allyl alcohols were observed to be resistant towards any reaction with this reagent³³.

Three Cr^{VI} reagents (ferric dichromate, polyvinylpyridine supported zinc dichromate, and polyvinylpyridine supported ferric dichromate) were prepared and found to be stable, mild and efficient reagents for the oxidation of different kinds of organic compounds³⁴. Of these, ferric dichromate seemed to be the most efficient. When taken in acetonitrile, ferric dichromate was able to oxidize styrene to benzaldehyde, and alcohols to their corresponding carbonyl compounds in good yields³⁴.

Quinolinium fluorochromate :

The synthetic potential of quinolinium fluorochromate (C₉H₇NHCrO₃F, QFC) and its application in the oxidation of alcohols was reported³⁵. QFC is soluble in water, DMF, DMSO and acetone. Primary alcohols are oxidized to aldehydes by QFC in dichloromethane at room temperature. The diverse types of organic substrates that have been oxidized by it³⁶ have highlighted the versatile nature of QFC. Recently, Chandrasekhar *et al.*³⁷ reported that QFC in dichloromethane is able to deprotect and oxidize the primary alcoholic group, while leaving the protected secondary alcoholic group intact. The protecting group is trialkylsilyl.

Quinolinium chlorochromate :

Quinolinium chlorochromate (QCC)³⁸ is prepared by treating a solution of CrO₃ in 6 M HCl with quinoline at 0°. The orange-red compound is stable to ordinary exposure to air, moisture and light. It efficiently oxidizes primary and secondary alcohols to the corresponding carbonyl compounds.

Mechanistic aspects

Most of the studies in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidations by complexed chromium(VI) compounds pertain to the halochromates and QCC. Some reports are available with other compounds also.

Hydroxy compounds :

The first reports about the kinetic and mechanism of the oxidation of alcohols was published in 1978. Banerji^{39,40} and Venkatasubramanian *et al.*⁴¹ reported the oxidation of

X = F, Cl, Br, OH
B = Heterocyclic base

Scheme 1

alcohols by PCC in 1 : 1 (v/v) dichloromethane and nitrobenzene solution. Both the groups of workers obtained similar kinetics. The reaction is first order with respect to PCC and the alcohol. Banerji^{39,40} found that the reactions are catalyzed by toluene-*p*-sulfonic acid (TsOH). The reactions exhibited negative reaction constants. The oxidation

Scheme 2

of deuteriated benzyl alcohol³⁹ and ethanol⁴⁰ showed the presence of substantial kinetic isotope effects. This confirmed the cleavage of an α-C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The authors suggested that the oxidation proceeded with a hydride ion transfer either directly or via a chromate ester (Schemes 1 and 2). The oxidation of cycloalkanols by PCC⁴² in chlorobenzene-nitrobenzene sol-

vent presented similar kinetics. The authors suggested, on the basis of the reactivity of the cyclalkanols and the effect of solvent, that probably a chromate ester mechanism is operative. To decide between the two alternative mechanisms, Banerji studied the temperature dependence of kinetic isotope effect in the oxidation of substituted benzhydrols⁴³ by PCC in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO). The kinetics are similar to those observed earlier. An analysis of the temperature-dependence of the kinetic isotope effect by the method of Kwart and Nickle⁴⁴, in the oxidation of benzhydrol, showed that the hydride-transfer takes place via a chromate ester through a symmetrical cyclic transition state (Scheme 2). Agarwal *et al.*²⁹ studied the oxidation of 2-pentanol by PCC in chloroform solution. They observed that kinetically the oxidation is comprised of two reactions. The first one consisted of the formation of a chromate ester and the second a decomposition of the ester. They obtained a kinetic isotope effect, $k_{\text{O-H}}/k_{\text{O-D}} = 1.30$, for the first reaction. In essence, their data supported a hydride-ion transfer via a chromate ester.

The oxidation of alcohols by PFC in acetonitrile-nitrobenzene or in DMSO presented a kinetic picture different than that observed in the oxidation by PCC. The first preliminary report on the oxidation of alcohols by PFC was published by Bhattacharjee *et al.*⁴⁵. They obtained a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the alcohols, and observed that the reactions were catalyzed by TsOH but could not determine the order with respect to the acid, as the reactions were very fast. A systematic study of the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols and of aliphatic alcohols by PFC in DMSO was reported by Banerji^{46,47}. He also observed a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to alcohols, suggesting the formation of an intermediate in a pre-equilibrium and its subsequent disproportionation in the rate-determining step. The oxidation of deuteriated ethanol⁴⁶ and benzyl alcohol⁴⁷ exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. This confirmed the cleavage of an α-C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The rates of the disproportionation of the intermediate, in the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols, showed an excellent correlation with Taft's⁴⁸ σ₁ and σ_R^{BA} substituent constants, while the *meta*-compounds correlated best with σ₁ and σ_R⁰ values. The oxidation of the *ortho*-substituted benzyl alcohols exhibited a steric acceleration. The oxidation of aliphatic alcohols is susceptible to both the polar and steric effects of the alkyl group. The polar reaction constants have negative values. The oxidation of benzyl alcohol⁴⁷ was studied in nineteen organic solvents. An analysis of the solvent effect, in terms of Swain's⁴⁹ equation, indicated the greater importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvents. In both the cases, in analysis of the temperature-dependence of the kinetic isotope effect indicated the presence of a symmetrical cyclic transition state in the rate-determining step of the oxidation. Thus, a

mechanism similar to the one depicted on Scheme 2 explained the experimental data. Though the formation of an intermediate ester is postulated in the oxidation by PCC also, the observed first order dependence on alcohol concentration can be explained by assuming that the value of the equilibrium constant, K_1 is very small and is, therefore, not reflected in the rate laws.

The oxidation of alcohols by PBC⁵⁰, BPCC⁵¹, QFC⁵², QCC⁵³ and QDC^{54,55} has also been studied. In general, the kinetics are similar to those observed in the oxidation by either PCC or PFC. The effect of hydrogen ions was studied in the oxidations by QDC, PBC, QFC, QCC and BPCC. The reactions are catalyzed by hydrogen-ions and the order with respect to $[H^+]$ is one in the case of QCC⁵³ and QDC^{54,55}, while with PBC^{50b,50c}, BPCC⁵¹ and QFC⁵², the hydrogen-ion dependence has the form.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[H^+] \quad (1)$$

Most of the workers have explained the hydrogen-ion dependence by assuming the formation of a protonated chromium(vi) species in a pre-equilibrium, with either both the unprotonated and protonated or only the protonated form being the reactive species. However, Aruna and Manikyamba⁵⁵ assumed a protonation of benzyl alcohol in its oxidation by QDC. In an oxidation reaction, the flow of electrons is from the reductant to the oxidant. It is hard to visualize a flow of electrons from a positively charged species to a neutral species. A protonated Cr^{VI} species is likely to be a better electrophile and oxidant as compared to the neutral one.

Wherever studied, the oxidation of deuteriated alcohols exhibited substantial primary kinetic isotope effects. Thus the cleavage of the α -C-H bond, in the rate-determining step, is confirmed. In many reactions, the effect of substituents on the rate has been studied. The reactions exhibited negative polar reaction constants with either single- or multi-parametric equations. In the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by QDC, Aruna and Manikyamba⁵⁵ obtained a smooth curve in Hammett plot. However, with the same system, i.e. benzyl alcohols and QDC, Dey and Mahanti^{54a} obtained a linear Hammett plot with the reaction constant being -1.67 . In the oxidations by PBC^{50b,50c}, BPCC⁵¹ and QFC⁵², the rates were obtained in different organic solvents and the analysis of the solvent effect indicated the greater importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvents. The temperature-dependence of the kinetic isotope effect, studied in a number of the reactions, indicated a symmetrical transition state in the rate-determining step of these oxidations. In the oxidation by QDC⁵⁴, the monomeric quinolinium chromate has been assumed as the reactive oxidizing species. One can conclude, therefore, that in general, the mechanism depicted in Scheme 2 accounts for all the observed data.

Recently, Kharpuria *et al.*⁵⁶ studied the kinetics of the

oxidation of two naturally occurring allyl alcohols, viz. geraniol and farnesol by QDC. The products were citral and farnesal, respectively. The kinetics are similar to those reported earlier. The olefinic bonds are not attacked. Mahanti *et al.* studied the oxidation of benzoin⁵⁷ and cyclic alcohols⁵⁸ also by QDC. The results follow the usual pattern and a mechanism depicted in Scheme 2 accounts for all the experimental results.

The oxidation of *vicinal*- and *non-vicinal*-diols by various halochromates, viz. PCC⁵⁹, PFC⁶⁰, PBC⁶¹, BPCC⁶² and QFC⁶³, in DMSO, has been studied. The product of the oxidation is the corresponding hydroxycarbonyl compound. The kinetics are similar to those observed in the oxidation of monohydric alcohols by corresponding oxidant. The oxidation of [1,1,2,2-²H₄]ethanediol (CD₂OH-CD₂OH) exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. Pinacol is not oxidized by any of these oxidants. The oxidation of *vicinal*-diols correlated well with the polar and steric substituent constants of the alkyl group⁵⁹⁻⁶³. The reaction is facilitated by the electron-donating power of the alkyl group and showed a steric acceleration. The oxidation of ethanediol, except by PCC⁵⁹, has been studied in different organic solvents. The results indicated that the diols behave like monohydric alcohols towards these oxidants. An analysis of the temperature-dependence of the kinetic isotope effect indicated that the mechanism depicted in Scheme 2 is operative in the oxidation of diols also.

The oxidation of diols by QDC⁶⁴ has been studied in aqueous acetic solution, in the presence of sulfuric acid. The kinetics are similar to those reported in the oxidation of monohydric alcohols. The reaction exhibited the rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = k [\text{diol}] [\text{QDC}] [H^+] \quad (2)$$

It has been proposed that the reactive oxidizing species is monomeric quinolinium chromate. Pinacol is oxidized by QDC yielding acetone. The oxidation of pinacol by QDC is proposed to involve the formation of a cyclic chromate ester, followed by a C-C bond cleavage. However, Littler⁶⁵ showed that the formation of a cyclic ester in the oxidation of diols by Cr^{VI} is a forbidden process. Interestingly, the oxidation of 1,2-cyclohexanediol by QDC⁶⁶ is not proposed to involve a cyclic ester. For the rest of the diols, a mechanism similar to that shown in Scheme 2 has been proposed. Mahanti *et al.*^{64,66} showed that a C-H bond cleavage is energetically preferable over a C-C bond cleavage.

The oxidation of D-glucose and some other monosaccharides by PFC⁶⁷ and PCC⁶⁸, in aqueous perchloric acid solution, has been reported. The reactions are first order with respect to each the oxidant, the sugar and hydrogen ions. In the oxidation by PCC⁶⁸ the products are γ -glucanolactone, formic acid and D-arabinose. This indicated that the reaction follows two pathways, i.e., one involving a C-H bond cleavage the other a C-C bond cleavage. The C-

H cleavage takes place by a hydride-ion transfer as envisaged for the alcohols. The C-C bond fission is proposed to proceed via a cyclic chromate ester. However, as stated earlier, an involvement of a cyclic chromate ester in chromium(VI) oxidation is not an allowed process⁶⁵.

The oxidation by PFC⁶⁷, on the other hand, yields only formic acid and D-arabinose. In the PFC oxidation, a solvent isotope effect, $k(D_2O)/k(H_2O) = 3.1$ has been obtained. The authors interpreted this in terms of two acid-catalyzed reactions : (i) the acid-catalyzed anomerization of α -D-glucose to β -D-glucose and (ii) a pre-equilibrium protonation of PFC. The authors suggested a bimolecular hydride-ion transfer in the rate-determining step. The carbocation so formed is postulated to form the ultimate products (but how?). It is not out of place to mention here that PCC and related reagents are salts of heterocyclic bases and the halochromic acids. In predominantly aqueous solutions, they are likely to undergo dissociation and/or hydrolysis and may ultimately result in the formation of chromic acid. One is, therefore, not quite sure of the nature of the oxidizing species.

Hydroxy acids :

α -Hydroxy acids can undergo oxidation by two different routes. They may behave like alcohols yielding oxoacids as the products, or may suffer oxidative decarboxylation to yield a carbonyl compound. The oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by PCC^{69,70}, PFC^{71,72}, PBC⁷³, BPCC⁷⁴ and QFC⁷⁵ in DMSO, has been studied. The oxidation of substituted mandelic acids, by PCC⁷⁰, PFC⁷², PBC⁷³, BPCC⁷⁴ and QFC⁷⁵ has been investigated to study the effect of structure on the reaction rate. The reactions are catalyzed by TsOH. It has been found with these complexed Cr^{VI} compounds, the hydroxy acids behave as alcohols, yielding the corresponding oxoacids as the products. The oxidations of α -deuteriomandelic acid (PhCDOHCOOH) and/or α,α -dideuterioglycollic acid (HOCD₂COOH) indicated the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect, thus confirming the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. Except in the oxidations by PCC^{69,70}, the rates were determined in nineteen different organic solvents and the results are reminiscent of those obtained in the oxidation of alcohols. The oxidation of substituted mandelic acids exhibited negative reaction constant indicating the presence of an electron-deficient reaction centre in the transition state. An analysis of the temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect points to the presence of a symmetrical transition state in the rate-determining step. Mechanisms, similar to that proposed for the oxidation of alcohols (Scheme 2), have been proposed for the oxidation of hydroxy acids also.

The oxidation of glycollic, lactic, benzilic, mandelic and tartaric acids by QDC in acids medium, with DMF as a solvent, has been studied recently^{76,77}. The results of the

oxidation of glycollic and lactic acids⁷⁶ are similar to those referred to above and a similar mechanism has been suggested. However, mandelic⁷⁷ and benzilic⁷⁶ acids undergo an oxidative decarboxylation to yield benzaldehyde and benzophenone, respectively. Tartaric acid⁷⁶ suffers a C-C bond cleavage to produce glyoxylic acid.

Phosphorus oxyacids :

The oxidation of three lower oxyacids of phosphorus, viz. phosphinic, phenylphosphinic and phosphorous acids by PFC⁷⁸, PCC⁷⁹, PBC⁸⁰, BPCC⁸¹, QFC⁸² and BTPPD⁸³ has been studied kinetically. The oxidation by PCC⁷⁹ and BPCC⁸¹ exhibited an overall second order, first with respect to each the oxidant and the oxyacid. The other reactions showed a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the reductants. These reactions did not induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile and further, an addition of the radical scavenger had no effect on the reaction rate. Thus, a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely. The oxidation of deuteriated phosphinic and phosphorous acids, by these oxidants, indicated the presence a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. This confirmed the rupture of a P-H bond in the rate-determining step. The reactions were studied in nineteen organic solvents. An

Scheme 3

analysis of the effect of solvents, in terms of multi-parametric linear solvation energy relationships, showed that the cation-solvation power of the solvents plays the major role. The phosphorus oxyacids are known to exist in two tautomeric forms, viz. the tri- and pentacoordinated forms. The role of the tautomers in the oxidation process was analyzed and the authors have concluded that in none of these reactions, the tricoordinated form is the reactive oxidizing species.

Scheme 4

The oxidation by PCC⁷⁹ and BPCC⁸¹ is proposed to involve a direct hydride-ion transfer from the reductant to the oxidant (Scheme 3). In the other oxidations, the kinetic results have indicated formation of an intermediate, in a rapid pre-equilibrium. It has been proposed that the intermediate may well be an anhydride, which subsequently disproportionates to the final products (Scheme 4). However, it must be pointed out that the oxidation by PCC and BPCC also may involve the formation of an anhydride, in the pre-equilibrium, with the equilibrium constant, K_1 , being very small.

Organic sulfides :

The first report about the oxidation of sulfides by a complexed Cr^{VI} compound was published by Panigrahi and Mahapatro⁸⁴. They reported the oxidation of dimethyl, dipropyl and diphenyl sulfides by PCC in chlorobenzene-nitrobenzene solution. The main product was the corresponding sulfoxide. The reaction showed a first order de-

Scheme 5

pendence on PCC and Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were obtained with respect to the sulfide. Later, Rajsekaran *et al.*⁸⁵ studied the kinetics of oxidation of several *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulfides (PMS) in chlorobenzene-nitrobenzene mixtures and also in 60% aqueous acetic acid. In the organic solvent, they obtained kinetics similar to those obtained by Panigrahi and Mahapatro⁸⁴. However, in aqueous acetic acid, the reaction was first order with respect to the sulfide. The correlation of the reaction rate with Hammett's σ values yielded negative reaction constants (-2.12 in aqueous acetic acid and -1.23 in the organic solvent mixture). The authors have proposed the same mechanism for the reaction in both the media. The proposed mechanism involves formation of an incipient sulfonium cation in the transition state (Scheme 5). It is surprising that the magnitude of the reaction constant in the organic solvent is less than in aqueous acetic acid. Since the latter is more polar, it is expected to stabilize the polar transition state much better than the organic solvents and consequently, the electronic demand on the substituent should be less. Thus the change of solvent may possibly bring about a change in the reactive species and/or the mechanism. It is perhaps not out of place to compare the results of the oxidation of substituted PMS by PCC in aqueous acetic acid with those by potassium dichromate in aqueous acetic acid in the presence of perchloric acid⁸⁶. The kinetics are similar in both the cases. The reaction con-

stants have almost identical values in both cases (-2.11 at 30° for the oxidation by chromic acid). This supports our view, stated earlier, that in predominantly aqueous medium, these complexed Cr^{VI} compounds may be ultimately hydrolyzed to chromic acid. Rajsekaran *et al.*⁸⁷ studied the oxidation of some *ortho*-substituted PMS also in 60% aqueous acetic acid and observed that the reaction is subjected to steric hindrance by the *ortho*-substituents.

The oxidation of substituted PMS, phenyl alkyl and diphenyl sulfides by PFC, in DMSO as a solvent, has been studied by Banerji⁸⁸. The oxidation is first order with respect to each, the oxidant and sulfide. The oxidation in nineteen different organic solvents showed that both cation- and anion-solvating powers play important roles. The rates of the oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted PMS showed an excellent correlation in terms of the Hammett equation, the reaction constants being negative. The rates of *ortho*-PMS, except those of *o*-COOH and *o*-COOMe compounds, correlated well in terms of Charton's equation⁸⁹. The reaction is subject to a steric hindrance by *ortho*-substituents. The deviation observed in the two compounds has been attributed to a moderate degree of anchimeric assistance provided by these groups to the reaction by stabilizing the positively polarized sulfur in the transition state. The electron-donating effect of alkyl groups, in the oxidation of phenyl alkyl sulfides, enhanced the rate of oxidations while the steric effect played a minor inhibitory role. A mechanism involving a rate-determining electrophilic oxygen transfer from PFC to the sulfide has been proposed (Scheme 6). The nucleophilic attack by the sulfide-sulfur on PFC may be viewed as an S_N2 process. Low magnitude of polar constants and the moderate degree of anchimeric assistance provided by the neighbouring

↓ Slow

Scheme 6

groups also supported this mechanism rather than the formation of a sulfonium cation (*cf.* Scheme 5). The oxidation of sulfides by PBC⁹⁰ has also been studied. The results are essentially similar to those obtained in the PFC⁸⁸ oxidation.

The oxidation of methionine, a sulfur-containing amino acid, by PCC⁹¹, PBC⁹² and BPCC⁹³ has been studied. Results show that methionine is oxidized to the corresponding sulfoxide and behaves like a sulfide towards these oxidants. A mechanism, similar to that proposed for the sulfides (Scheme 6) accounted for the experimental results.

In a recent report on the kinetics of the oxidation of or-

ganic sulfides by pyridinium dichromate (PDC) in acetonitrile, Meenakshisundaram and Amutha⁹⁴ observed, in the case of diethyl sulfide, a first order dependence on PDC and sulfide but a second order dependence on TsOH. In case of aryl methyl sulfides, the order with respect to TsOH is >1 and <2 , while Michaelis-Menten type kinetic were observed with respect to the sulfide. A non-linear Hammett plot was obtained with both electron-donating and electron-withdrawing groups slowing down the rate of reaction. The reaction was retarded by acrylonitrile, thereby indicating a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals. The authors have suggested the following mechanism with reaction (4) as the rate-determining step of electron-withdrawing groups, and reaction (5) for electron-releasing groups,

Hydrocarbons :

The oxidation of toluene and substituted toluenes by QDC⁹⁵⁻⁹⁷ and PFC⁹⁸ has been reported. The reaction is first order with respect to the oxidant. However, the order with respect to the reductant is dependent on the nature of the oxidant. With PFC, it is less than one, while QDC oxidation showed a first order dependence on the hydrocarbon. The

oxidations of deuteriated toluene exhibited considerable primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.0-6.2$). Thus the cleavage of a C-H bond, in the rate-determining step, was confirmed. A correlation with Hammett equation yielded a reaction constant of -2.0 (at 303 K) for the PFC oxidation. However, the QDC oxidation of substituted toluenes^{96,97} and methoxytoluenes⁹⁵ was almost insensitive to the nature and position of the substituent ($\rho = -0.2$). Though the induced polymerization of acrylonitrile and ESR studies failed to yield any evidence for the generation of free radicals, the authors have suggested a hydrogen abstraction mechanism for the oxidations. Both the groups of workers have proposed a mechanism involving a resonance hybrid as an intermediate (Scheme 7).

The oxidation of naphthalene⁹⁹ and fluorene¹⁰⁰ by QDC have been studied in DMF containing perchloric acid. The rate law has the following form,

$$\text{Rate} = k[\text{QDC}] [\text{hydrocarbon}] [\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

The oxidation of naphthalene-*d*₈ showed the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect, confirming the rupture of a C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The values of the reaction constants, for the oxidation of substituted naphthalenes and fluorene were -1.30 and -1.50 , respectively. ESR measurements indicated the formation of a Cr^V intermediate in the reactions. Thus a hydrogen abstraction mechanism, leading to the formation of a free radical and a Cr^V species, has been proposed.

Sarma and Mahanti¹⁰¹ studied the oxidation of substituted phenanthrene by QDC. The kinetics are similar to those observed in the oxidation of other hydrocarbons. However, the magnitude of the reaction constant was higher (-1.79) than those observed in the oxidation of toluenes or fluorenes. The authors have suggested that the oxidation of phenanthrene involved a hydride-ion transfer in the rate-determining step.

The oxidation of substituted styrenes by QDC¹⁰², in acidic DMF, showed the usual kinetics. The oxidation resulted in the formation of benzaldehyde and formaldehyde. A small inverse kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 0.80$) was observed in the oxidation of β,β -dideuterio-styrene. A correlation with σ values yielded a reaction constant of -4.0 . This indicated the formation of a carbocationic intermediate in the rate-determining step. Subsequent cleavage of the C-C bond yielded the final products (Scheme 8).

Amino acids :

Karim and Mahanti¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁶ studied the oxidation of several α -amino acids by QDC in DMF in aqueous sulfuric acid solution. The main product of the oxidation is the corresponding cyanide. The reaction shows a first order dependence on QDC, amino acid and hydrogen ions. The oxidation of α -deuterioamino acids indicated the absence of a kinetic isotope effect. Hence the α -C-H bond is not cleaved in the rate-determining step. It has been proposed that under the reaction conditions employed, the amino acid exists mainly in the form of a cationic species. A mechanism, involving the formation of an anhydride and its subsequent breakdown has been proposed (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

Aldehydes :

Reports are available about the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by QFC¹⁰⁷ and PCC¹⁰⁸ in aqueous acetic acid solution. The oxidation of benzaldehydes¹⁰⁹ by PFC and of aliphatic aldehydes by PFC¹¹⁰, PBC¹¹¹, QFC¹¹² and BPCC¹¹³ in DMSO has also been reported.

The oxidations in aqueous acetic acid are first order in each, the aldehyde, PCC/QFC and hydrogen ions. The correlation with Hammett's σ values and with Taft's dual substituent-parameter (DSP) equation yielded positive reaction constants. The authors proposed a mechanism involving the formation of a chromate ester, in the pre-equilibrium, followed by its decomposition, catalyzed by a water molecule, in the rate-determining step. However, as per the proposed mechanism, the slow step is preceded by a fast reversible formation of a chromate ester and the observed effect of structure on rate is composite factor representing the effect on both the equilibrium and the slow step. It is difficult to assign any mechanistic significance to the values of the reaction constants.

In the oxidations by PFC^{109,110} in DMSO, Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were observed with respect to the aldehyde. The equilibrium constants for the complex formation and the rates of their disproportionation have been evaluated. The oxidation of deuteriated aldehydes (PhCDO and MeCDO) exhibited substantial kinetic isotope effects, confirming the cleavage of the aldehydic C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The rate constants of the disproportionation of the intermediate in the oxidation of *meta*-substituted benzaldehydes correlated well with Taft's⁴⁸ σ_1 and σ_R^0 values, while the *para*-compounds exhibited an excel-

Scheme 10

lent correlation with σ_1 and σ_R^+ values. The oxidation of the *ortho*-compounds showed a correlation with Taft's⁴⁸ σ_1 , σ_R^+ and Charton's⁸⁶ steric parameter, *V*. The polar reaction constants were negative. The reaction is subject a steric hindrance by the *ortho*-substituent. The oxidation of the aliphatic aldehydes correlated well with Taft's σ^+ values with negative reaction constant. The negative polar reaction constants, correlation with σ_R^+ values and the substantial kinetic isotope effect indicated a carbocationic state in the rate-determining step. A mechanism involving a hydride ion transfer has been proposed (Scheme 10). It is difficult to reconcile the differences in the reports¹⁰⁷⁻¹¹². However, in the oxidations by QFC¹⁰⁷ and PCC¹⁰⁸, there is no evidence for a C-H bond rupture in the rate-determining step. The formation of the chromate ester may well be the rate-determining step.

Acids :

The oxidation of some carboxylic acids, other than

Scheme 11

hydroxy and amino acids, has also been studied. The oxidation of maleic and fumaric acids by QDC in acid medium in DMF¹¹⁴ showed a first order dependence on each, QDC, the substrate and hydrogen ions. It has been proposed that the reaction involves an electrophilic attack by QDCH⁺ on the C=C bond to yield a cyclic ester which decomposes in the subsequent fast step to yield the ultimate product formaldehyde.

Oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by PBC¹¹⁵, PFC¹¹⁶, PCC¹¹⁷, BPCC¹¹⁸ and QFC¹¹⁹ using DMSO as the solvent, has been studied. The reactions exhibited Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the organic acids. The oxidation of deuterioformic acid (DCOOH) showed the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect, confirming the rupture of the C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The oxidation of formic acid was studied in nineteen organic solvents. An analysis of the solvent effect in terms of Swain's equation⁴⁹, indicated the greater role of cation-solvation in the oxidation process. It has been observed that the entropies of formation of the intermediate complex, in the oxidations of oxalic acid, were much more negative than those in the oxidation of formic acid. This indicated the formation of a more rigid intermediate in the case of oxalic acid. The authors proposed that the oxidation of oxalic acid involves formation of a cyclic anhydride and its subsequent disproportionation (Scheme 11).

The oxidation of thioacids by PCC¹²⁰, PFC¹²¹, BPCC¹²², PBC¹²³ and QFC¹²⁴ has been studied. The solvent was DMSO. The main product of the oxidation was the corresponding disulfide-dimer. The reactions exhibited Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the thioacid. The reactions were catalyzed by TsOH and the acid-dependence had the form shown in eq. (1). The oxidations were studied in various organic solvents and the analysis of the data indicates the greater importance of the cation-solvation. It was proposed that a thioester is formed in the pre-equilibrium, which decomposed in the slow step to yield a sulfenium cation. The acid-catalysis has been attributed to the protonation of the thioester, prior to its decomposition.

Other compounds :

The kinetics of the oxidation of substituted benzylamines¹²⁵ by QDC in DMF, in the presence of sulfuric acid, has been studied. The reaction was first order in each, the amine, QDC and hydrogen ions. The oxidation of deuteriated benzylamine (PhCD₂NH₂) indicated the presence of a considerable kinetic isotope effect. The value of ρ was -0.25. Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile was not observed. The formation of an intermediate, having a Cr-N bond, was proposed. The intermediate decomposed to yield the corresponding benzaldehyde as the final product.

The oxidation of diphenylamine¹²⁶ by QDC in the presence of dichloroacetic acid, exhibited Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the amine. The main

product was tetraphenylhydrazine. The reaction is catalyzed by the acid. The value of ρ was -1.2. The reaction was proposed to proceed through an intermediate complex, having a Cr-N bond, which broke down to diphenylhydroxylamine. This was oxidized, in fast steps, to the final product.

The oxidation of some benzyl ethers by PFC¹²⁷ in glacial acetic acid, in the presence of sulfuric acid, was first order in each PFC, the ether and hydrogen ions. The value of reaction constant was -0.52. The authors suggested a direct hydride-ion transfer from the ether to protonated PFC (*cf.* Scheme 1) in the rate-determining step. However, formation of a carbocationic transition state is doubtful, in view of the low magnitude of the reaction constant.

The oxidation of substituted 2-phenylthiazolidines¹²⁸ to the corresponding sulfoxides, by PCC in glacial acetic acid, exhibited Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the reductant. The equilibrium constants of the complex formation and the rate constants of their decomposition were determined. The authors attempted to correlate the rate constant in terms of Taft's⁴⁸ and Swain's¹²⁹ DSP equations but the correlations were not satisfactory. However, formation of an electron-deficient reaction centre has been indicated. The proposed mechanism was similar to one proposed earlier for the oxidation of sulfides (Scheme 6).

The oxidation of styryl ketones by PCC¹³⁰ in 90% acetic acid, in the presence of perchloric acid, led to the formation of the epoxides. The reaction was first order in each, the oxidant, H⁺ and the ketone. The rates correlated well with Brown's σ^+ values with fractional negative reaction constants. The authors suggested that the reaction proceeds through a 'three-centre' type intermediate.

The oxidation of several aromatic anils by QCC¹³¹ in aqueous acetic acid has been reported recently. The reaction is first order in the anil and QCC and second order with respect to hydrogen ions. The value of apparent reaction constant is -2.2.

Scheme 12

Kinetics of the oxidative regeneration of carbonyl compounds from oximes by PFC¹³² and PCC¹³³ has been studied recently. The reactions exhibited first order depend-

ence on both the oxidant and oxime. Low enthalpies and large negative entropies of activation characterize the reactions. The rates of oxidation of aldoximes correlate well with Pavelich-Taft dual substituent parameter equation. The low positive value of the polar reaction constant indicates a nucleophilic attack by a chromate-oxygen on the carbon leading to the formation of cyclic intermediate (Scheme 12).

Acknowledgement

This article was mainly prepared during the stay of one of the authors (K.K.B.) at North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong, as a U.G.C. Visiting Fellow, during the summer 1999. Thanks are due to the authorities of the University for the hospitality and facilities.

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